

**LEMIERRE SYNDROME COMPLICATED BY CERVICOFACIAL NECROTIZING INFECTION –
CASE REPORT**

Andreea Monica FILIP,
MD, Braila County Emergency Clinical Hospital
Dorina STAN,
MD, Braila County Emergency Clinical Hospital
Puşica ZAINEA,
PhD student,
Braila County Emergency Clinical Hospital
Adrian DRAGAN,
PhD student,
Braila County Emergency Clinical Hospital
Dragoş F. VOICU
MD, PhD.,
Braila County Emergency Clinical Hospital
Associated Profesor
“Dunarea de Jos” University, Galati – Romania

Abstract

Background: Lemierre syndrome is a rare but potentially fatal condition characterized by septic thrombophlebitis of the internal jugular vein, most commonly following an oropharyngeal infection caused by *Fusobacterium necrophorum*.

Case presentation: We report the case of a 34-year-old previously healthy patient who presented with severe sepsis following an untreated pharyngitis. The clinical course was complicated by cervicofacial necrotizing fasciitis, internal jugular vein thrombosis, and septic pulmonary emboli.

Management and outcome: The patient required emergency surgical intervention with extensive debridement and drainage, broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy, anticoagulation, and intensive supportive care.

Conclusions: Early recognition, aggressive surgical management, and multidisciplinary care are essential to improve outcomes in severe forms of Lemierre syndrome.

Keywords: Lemierre syndrome; *Fusobacterium necrophorum*; sepsis

1. Introduction

Lemierre syndrome, first described by André Lemierre in 1936, is a rare but severe complication of oropharyngeal infections [1]. It is characterized by septic thrombophlebitis of the internal jugular vein and metastatic septic emboli, most commonly affecting the lungs [2,3].

Although historically considered a “forgotten disease” due to widespread antibiotic use, its incidence appears to be increasing in recent years [4].

2. Case Report

A 34-year-old male patient with no significant past medical history presented to the emergency department with: high fever (39.5°C), severe odynophagia, left temporomandibular swelling with fistulization, altered general condition (fig. 1-2)

Fig. 1-2

Symptoms had begun approximately 7 days prior and were initially treated symptomatically at home, without antibiotics.

Clinical examination: toxic appearance, tachycardia: 110 bpm, hypotension: 100/60 mmHg, left cervical

pain with extension along the sternocleidomastoid muscle, hyperemic pharynx without visible purulent exudate.

Laboratory findings leukocytosis: 23,500/mm³ with neutrophilia, elevated CRP and procalcitonin, electrolyte imbalance (hyponatremia, hyperkalemia, hypocalcemia,

hypomagnesemia), metabolic acidosis with increased anion gap.

Blood cultures identified *Fusobacterium necrophorum*.

Contrast-enhanced cervico-thoracic CT revealed thrombosis of the right internal jugular vein and multiple peripheral pulmonary nodules suggestive of septic emboli.

The diagnosis of Lemierre syndrome was established based on:

- recent oropharyngeal infection

- identification of anaerobic pathogen
- internal jugular vein thrombosis
- septic pulmonary emboli

Surgical treatment

Emergency surgery was performed under local anesthesia, due to the severity and extent of infection. The following procedures were undertaken:

- excision of fistulous tract (fig. 3-4)
- incision and drainage of purulent collections
- opening of involved fascial spaces: pterygomandibular, submandibular, genian (supra- and sub-buccinator), infratemporal
- extensive excisional debridement to viable tissue (fig. 5)
- extraction of tooth 2.8 (without oroantral communication)

Fig. 3-4

Fig. 5

Medical treatment: broad-spectrum antibiotics (carbapenem-based regimen – Imipenem or equivalent)

- anti-inflammatory and analgesic therapy
- hydroelectrolytic and acid-base correction
- cardiovascular support
- oxygen therapy
- gastric protection
- vitamin supplementation (B-complex and C-vitamin)
- mucolytics (N-acetylcysteine)
- anticoagulation (Enoxaparin 0.4–0.6 mL once or twice daily)

Local care

- repeated intraoperative lavage (hydrogen peroxide, saline, antiseptics)
- drainage tubes
- daily postoperative irrigation with povidone-iodine.

The patient's evolution was favorable, with discharge in the course of local healing two weeks postoperatively (fig. 6-7)

Fig. 6-7

3. Discussion

Lemierre syndrome is most commonly caused by *Fusobacterium necrophorum*, an anaerobic Gram-negative bacillus that colonizes the oropharynx [2,5].

The pathophysiology involves:

primary oropharyngeal infection, invasion of the lateral pharyngeal space, septic thrombophlebitis of the internal jugular vein, hematogenous dissemination with septic emboli [3,7].

Severe complications, including necrotizing soft tissue infections and even gas-forming infections, although rare, have been reported in the literature [8].

Early recognition is essential, as delayed diagnosis is associated with increased morbidity and mortality [4,7].

This case illustrates a severe and atypical presentation of Lemierre syndrome, complicated by cervicofacial necrotizing fasciitis and features suggestive of gas-forming infection.

Such complications are rare but may occur due to: septic thrombosis, tissue ischemia, rapid spread of anaerobic infection.

The disease progression is often fulminant, with potential complications including: mediastinitis, cavernous sinus thrombosis, pulmonary abscesses, cerebral abscesses.

Management requires a multidisciplinary approach involving:

- oral and maxillofacial surgery
- otorhinolaryngology
- intensive care
- general surgery

Management of Lemierre syndrome also requires early administration of broad-spectrum antibiotics with anaerobic coverage, most commonly targeting *Fusobacterium necrophorum* [2,5].

The role of anticoagulation remains controversial but may be considered in selected cases with extensive thrombosis [6].

A notable aspect of this case is the extensive surgical intervention performed under local anesthesia in

a resource-limited setting, while still adhering to key surgical principles:

- wide drainage, aggressive debridement,
- effective control of the septic focus.

4. Conclusions

Lemierre syndrome associated with cervicofacial necrotizing infection represents a life-threatening condition requiring immediate intervention.

Early diagnosis, prompt initiation of appropriate antibiotic therapy, and aggressive surgical management are critical for patient survival.

This case emphasizes the importance of rapid septic focus control and coordinated multidisciplinary care in managing severe infections of oropharyngeal origin.

References

1. Lemierre A. On certain septicaemias due to anaerobic organisms. *Lancet*. 1936;227(5874):701–703.
2. Riordan T. Human infection with *Fusobacterium necrophorum* (necrobacillosis), with a focus on Lemierre's syndrome. *Clin Microbiol Rev*. 2007;20(4):622–659.
4. Karkos PD, Asrani S, Karkos CD, Leong SC, Theochari EG, Alexopoulou TD, et al. Lemierre's syndrome: a systematic review. *Laryngoscope*. 2009;119(8):1552–1559.
5. Johannesen KM, Bodtger U. Lemierre's syndrome: current perspectives on diagnosis and management. *Infect Drug Resist*. 2016; 9:221–227.
6. Wright WF, Shiner CN, Ribes JA. Lemierre syndrome. *South Med J*. 2012;105(5):283–288.
7. Phua CK, Chadachan VM, Acharya R. Lemierre syndrome—should we anticoagulate? A case report and review of the literature. *Int J Angiol*. 2013;22(2):137–142.
8. Hagelskjaer Kristensen L, Prag J. Lemierre's syndrome and other disseminated *Fusobacterium necrophorum* infections in Denmark: a prospective epidemiological and clinical survey. *Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis*. 2008;27(8):779–789.
9. Eilbert W, Singla N. Lemierre's syndrome. *Int J Emerg Med*. 2013;6:40.